

A Reflection of His Father

NOIRLab's new Assistant Scientist Guillermo Damke is following in his father's footsteps and pursuing his dreams

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Guillermo Damke recalls the moments of just him and the truly dark night sky unveiling the stars and a glowing band of light above him. These moments of solitude transformed into moments of awakening, as Guillermo desired to know the secrets beyond Earth.

Guillermo's father (also named Guillermo Damke) fueled his wonder of space with alluring images of nebulae and spiral galaxies that were featured in pamphlets he would bring home from his job with AURA.

As a miner left unemployed by the impact of the Chilean economic crisis of 1982, Guillermo's father eventually found stability that December as a contractor for AURA at the Cerro Tololo Inter-American Observatory (CTIO). He worked various jobs in the Recinto from landscaping to painting and later helped in the warehouse with shipments coming from the United States. In 1984 a position within AURA opened and Guillermo's father started working as an AURA employee that May. After 34 years of dedicated service, he retired in January 2018. He was Guillermo's greatest influence, providing the spark and fuel needed to foster his ambition of becoming an astronomer and forge his own path.

Guillermo grew up in La Serena, Chile. He was naturally curious about the way things worked from objects such as radios and car engines to the intricate details of machines and the complexities of the natural world. In primary school, Guillermo enjoyed studying the natural sciences and recalls his excitement upon seeing the first images of Jupiter and Saturn released by Voyager I. Guillermo's school was known for its prestigious physics teacher, Padre Juan Bautista Picetti, who became his high school mentor and inspired generations of astronomers with the observatory on the top of the renowned Seminario Conciliar in La Serena. As a fourth grader, Guillermo made his first observation of Jupiter with the observatory's 8-inch telescope. By the time he was in seventh grade, he was a member of the school's astronomy academy and made observations every Friday night.

Guillermo and his family were aware of the challenges in becoming not just an astronomer but a *Chilean* astronomer in particular. In the early 1990s, most astronomers were from the United States and had access to extensive scientific resources. With the certainty of knowing he wanted to be an astronomer, Guillermo explored all avenues to accessing astronomical knowledge. The AURA pamphlets were a start, but books were expensive and there was no internet, making resources limited. In middle school Guillermo had two astronomy books: a generic book from his uncle and Carl Sagan's *Cosmos* from his aunt. In high school he took advantage of his father's connections, and was able to access all the books within the CTIO library.

During Guillermo's final year of high school, instructors were needed to operate a traveling planetarium that had been shipped to La Serena. Guillermo and his friend, Carlos Corco

Seven-year-old Guillermo with his family (parents and two older sisters) in 1989 standing in front of an AURA warehouse. Credit: G. Damke (NOIRLab)

Guillermo and his father on the catwalk of the Gemini South telescope, while it was still under construction in 1998. *Credit: G. Damke (NOIRLab)*

(who now works for the Southern Astrophysical Research Telescope), took advantage of this opportunity and agreed to lead planetarium presentations at the local schools. Guillermo continued these outreach events throughout his undergraduate experience and had access to even more resources when a second planetarium was obtained by Gemini South in 2003. Through engaging hundreds of people through outreach, he gained confidence in public speaking and learned the art of communicating complex ideas.

Guillermo attended the University of La Serena for his bachelor's in physics with a minor in astronomy. In parallel with his undergraduate studies, Guillermo took courses to learn the English language, realizing this was important if he wanted to be an astronomer. During his final year at the University of La Serena, Guillermo was selected to participate in CTIO's Prácticas de

Investigación en Astronomía (PIA) program. As part of this intensive 10-week summer program, Guillermo had a first-hand, collaborative experience of what life, research, and operations were like at a major international observatory. It was a life-changing experience to learn from the same astronomers that he had looked up to and that were considered part of his family as a result of his father's position at AURA. As a testimony to Guillermo's work within the PIA program, Armin Rest, currently an associate astronomer at STScI, offered him a research assistant position at AURA with some work dedicated to the planetarium operations for Gemini South.

Guillermo's impact at AURA and Gemini led to a Fulbright Scholarship, providing him the opportunity to pursue astronomical research at a globally ranked institution. Guillermo attended the University of Virginia for his doctorate where he researched the spectroscopy of different Milky Way structures and tidal streams in the Sagittarius dwarf galaxy. Guillermo earned his PhD in 2016 and began work as a postdoctoral researcher for the commissioning of the APOGEE-South spectrograph, part of the Sloan Digital Sky Survey-III. In 2017 he was hired as an astronomer of data science for AURA and the University of La Serena.

Today, Guillermo is a NOIRLab assistant scientist providing user support for Blanco's Dark Energy Camera (DECam) at CTIO, where he is also in charge of site protection efforts to counteract light pollution. Part of Guillermo's initiative is to provide students with similar life-changing opportunities to his own experiences. As one of the leads of the [La Serena School of Data Science](#), Guillermo inspires the next generation of scientists

with the importance and future of "Big Data" in astronomy. The school provides senior undergraduates and early graduate students with intensive hands-on experiences learning how big astronomical datasets are processed, accessed, and analyzed utilizing reduction pipelines, databases, and scientific programming.

Guillermo is the mirror image of his father, exactly the same but in reverse. They have mutual respect and pride in each other's journey. Guillermo knows the lengths his father went through behind the scenes to help put a telescope into operation for an astronomer to use, from loading trucks to working weekends for a shipment to go up the mountain. In the reflection of his image, Guillermo's father sees his son, the astronomer who is living his dream to uncover the wonders of the Universe.

Guillermo with a telescope around 1997 while visiting ACHAYA with his father. ACHAYA is an association of Chilean amateur astronomers, based in Santiago about 300 miles south of La Serena. *Credit: G. Damke(NOIRLab)*